

Extremism and Terrorism in Pakistan in 21st Century: Changing Dynamics, New Challenges, Security Governance, Viable Policy Option

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Abstract

Pakistan is playing the role of frontline state in countering terrorism at global level .The trends in terrorism are diversity ,decentralization ,democratization ,disinformation, economic depression and violation of human rights are shaping the future of violent extremism and terrorism . The terrorism is emerged in various forms: kidnappings, hijacking ,bomb scares ,bombing ,assassinations ,cyber attacks and use of chemicals ,biological ,nuclear and radiological weapons etc . There are new trends of extremism and terrorism in newly emerging districts of Pakistan.The Pakistani state is confronting the external and internal challenges, traditional and non-traditional security threats with new dimensions and dynamism. These issues are related to security governance of the state. There are viable policy options and pragmatic strategies to counterterrorism in Pakistan. The research work will rely on books, research papers, magazines and internet websites etc. The study is divided in introduction, literature review, objectives, research questions, methodology and conclusion. The situational approach will be applied to gauge various dimensions of terrorism in Pakistan. The aggression frustration theory will be applied in this research to assess terrorist behavior. The strategic model of terrorism will be applied that terrorists attack civilian population and inflict harm masses and public places.The data will be analyzed in the light of above facts to draw the conclusion.

Keywords: Terrorism, Changing Dynamics, Security Governance, Policy Options

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